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XIX Міжнародна наукова конференція студентів,
молодих вчених та фахівців

**АКТУАЛЬНІ ПИТАННЯ
СУЧАСНОЇ МЕДИЦИНИ**

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(15-16 грудня 2022 року, м. Харків, Україна)

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named after SI. V.T. Zaitsev of the National Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine” about HH from 2019 to 2021. The age of the patients ranged from 24 to 73 years. The main complaints of the patients were: belching in 40 (95.2%), heartburn in 37 (88%), nausea in 24 (57.1%), chest pain in 12 (28.5%), pain radiating to neck, shoulders or back in 10 (23.85) patients. All patients underwent an X-ray examination of the gastrointestinal tract, which made it possible to identify and determine the type of hernia, determine its degree, study the function of the esophageal-gastric junction, determine the topography of anatomical formations, as well as their location, displacement and identify the presence of complications. X-ray examination of the gastrointestinal tract included a survey roentgenoscopy of the chest and abdominal organs, examination of the upper gastrointestinal tract with a liquid and thick barium suspension in the vertical position of patients and in the horizontal position of patients with a lowered head end.

Results: All patients underwent X-ray examination of the gastrointestinal tract with barium suspension. In 12 (28.5%) patients, I degree HH was detected (the abdominal esophagus protrudes into the chest cavity, the cardia is at the level of the diaphragm; in 22 (52.3%) patients, degree II HH was detected (the cardia is located above the diaphragm, and folds of the gastric mucosa are detected in the diaphragmatic opening); in 8 (19.2%) patients, the III degree of HH was detected (a part of the stomach or the entire organ with the abdominal esophagus is determined in the chest cavity). Of these, fixed HH (II-III degree) was detected in 16 (38%) patients, sliding in 26 (62%) patients. All patients with grade I and 20 (47%) patients with grade II underwent conservative treatment and 10 (24%) patients with grade II-III underwent surgical treatment.

Conclusion: Thus, a polypositional X-ray examination of the gastrointestinal tract with a barium suspension allows you to determine the type of HH and its degree. In a retrospective analysis of case histories, it was found that II degree HH occurs most often. Timely detection of the presence of HH, its type and degree allows you to choose the optimal technique and the amount of conservative or surgical treatment.

LIGHT BEARER: PHYSICIAN IN SANSKRIT ETYMOLOGY

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Introduction. Etymology can sometimes shed light on those parts of our history, on which we have no other sources. The older the language is, the deeper into the past it can get its researchers. One of the oldest documented languages is Sanskrit, the ancient lingua franca of South East Asia. The study of the etymology of Sanskrit words for medical profession can reveal details on the ways physicians were perceived by ancient people. This topic didn't get deserved attention in the History of Medicine, which makes it important and relevant.

The aim of the study. The aim of the study is to reveal wider etymological understanding of the words for physician in Sanskrit.

Materials and methods. The study is based on the works of renown scholars of Sanskrit etymology and is conducted using basic etymological methods.

Results. Sanskrit has three words, that are relevant to the English word physician: oshadhipati, cikitsaka and vaidya. These words can be further deconstructed into separate root-words, which can lead to deeper meanings. The word oshadhipati means lord of herbs or a physician. It is formed with two root-words: osha (shining) and pati (lord). Closely related words in Sankrit are: oshadhi (light-containing, medicinal herb, remedy); oshadhi garbha (producer of herbs, living among herbs as snake). The latter one is particularly interesting, since snake is the most ancient symbol of medicine. The word cikitsaka has only one meaning in Sanskrit (physician), but its root-word (cikit) has multiple meanings (knowing, experienced, shining) and involved in many word formations, like: cikitsana (curing); cikitsa (practice or science of medicine); cikitsita (cured); cikitsu (wise, treating medically); cikitsya (curable); cikitu (understanding); cikitvan (attentive); cikitvas (observing, knowing, understanding, experienced, shining) and many others. The word vaidya has a wide array of meanings: versed in science, learned, medical, medicinal, relating to medicine, an expert (especially in medicine), skilled in the art of healing, a physician, etc. This word comes from the root-word veda, which forms many words related to knowledge, science and philosophy. One of this words is vedati (to call, cry out, curse, swear), which has similar spelling as the Proto-Slavic vedati (to know) and similar meaning to the Proto-Slavic vrat (to swear, to curse), from which comes one of the Proto-Slavic word for physician (vratch).

Conclusion. The three Sanskrit words, which stand for the same phenomenon as English word physician, have a very interesting etymology. Two of them (oshadhipati and cikitsaka) have similar meanings and can be understood as “containing light”, “shining” or “an expert of herbs”. The latter one (cikitsaka) has similarities with the third word (vaidya) in that they both are related to the state of being experienced, wise and observing. All of the studied words lead us to the understanding of an ancient East Asian physician as an educated person, well versed in the healing properties of herbs.

CAVERNOUS MESENTERIC HEMANGIOMA THAT WASN'T DIAGNOSED DURING LIFE

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Introduction. Hemangiomas are rare benign tumors that are usually congenital. The tumor is characterized by asymptomatic course. Internal hemangiomas are more likely to be present as accidental findings at autopsy. Complications of hemangiomas can be infection, thrombosis, ulceration. That is why the study of each case of postmortem diagnosis of hemangiomas of the abdominal cavity is relevant.

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